

Exploring Issues in AI-Powered Language Teaching and Learning in Uzbekistan

Dr. T. Shafeek*

Assistant Professor of Linguistics, Ministry of Preschool and School Education, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

*Corresponding Author

Dr. T. Shafeek

Assistant Professor of Linguistics, Ministry of Preschool and School Education, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.

Article History

Received: 24.09.2024

Accepted: 05.10.2024

Published: 16.10.2024

Abstract: Artificial intelligence (AI), one of technological advancements to impact in day today's lives, is being adopted or used for teaching and learning English language. Unlike developed countries such as the U.S.A and China which have AI-led technology for effective Teaching Learning with AI- powered tools, a few schools in Uzbekistan have only prioritized use of AI-powered tools. However, issues are yet to address while adopting AI assisted teaching aids. This paper aims at discussing potential issues while integrating AI- powered Language Teaching technologies in classrooms. Much of discussions presented in this papers is purely based on the speaker's five month observations at School 205, Mirzo Ulugbek, Tashkent. Most importantly, potential BWA (Before, While and After) issues while incorporating the AI -assisted teaching tools in classrooms. B- issues include funding of Public authorities, conventional attitude and belief towards technology, ethical and social concerns and lack of increased trainings for teachers for optimized teaching- learning. W(hile) potential issues consists of heavy and sophisticated link with intelligent algorithm, malfunctioning or disruption of technology, incorrect outputs due to supply of inaccurate data etc. A(fter)- issues include shortage of AI specialists, passivation of AI tools, less monitoring, unrewarding etc.

Keywords: AI Assisted, Language Teaching Technology, Issues.

Cite this article:

Shafeek, T., (2024). Exploring Issues in AI-Powered Language Teaching and Learning in Uzbekistan. *ISAR Journal of Arts, Humanities and Social Sciences*, 2(10), 29-31.

1. Introduction

For any effective language Teaching-Learning, technology is undoubtedly an intrinsic part of the past, current and future educational curriculum whether or not it is a state board or international boards such as Cambridge, Edexcel and IB.

Thanks to technology for roles it plays on the platforms of current language teaching learning. On one hand, advancements in technology undoubtedly create more new possibilities and help both teaching and learning process is more fun game-based and engaging. For example, Kahoot, an Artificial Intelligence- powered game based platform for teaching learning, is an essential tool most of advanced institutions in India and other countries for learners. On the other hand, AI (Artificial Intelligence) powered learning apps like Kahoot, Duolingo (for language learning) e.t.c. have not been productive as expected even at top rated schools that support only technology integrated teaching learning. This paper tries to discuss issues while using AI- Powered Language teaching technology. Apart from the definition of Artificial intelligence, a short note on AI assisted and AI- Led applications are also included. AI-assisted technology is mainly referred to established smart boards. For sequential purpose, issues are categorized as BWA (Before, While and After). Having explored potential issues of AI powered tools, there is a scope for suggestion for resolving certain issues that are unaddressed.

2. Artificial Intelligence (AI)

AI, a technological innovation, is linked to complex algorithm capable enough to complete or perform tasks that are associated with intelligent beings.

Popenici and Kerr in *The Impact of Artificial Intelligence on Learning, Teaching, and Education* defines artificial intelligence (AI) as "computing systems that are able to engage in human-like processes such as learning, adapting, synthesizing, self-correction and use of data for complex processing tasks"(p.7).

They view AI as "a machine that thinks, understands languages, solves problems, diagnoses medical conditions, keeps cars on the highways, plays chess, and paints impressionistic imitations of van Gogh paintings."(p.7)

2.1. AI in Foreign Language Teaching

Advancement in Language Technology, AI-assisted inventions are in particular, have been developed for effective and creative language teaching. Automated speech, auto corrections and auto recognitions of inputs, identifying and recognizing words, phrases and sentences, locating and extracting data from texts or images or recordings, transferring, making inferences or imparting them to their right source etc. are some of many jobs that AI facilitates in AI powered Second Language Technology.

2.2. AI- Assisted vs. AI – Driven

iPhone's Siri, which you are very familiar with, is the best example for AI – assisted technology. The presence of human beings is required for performing the tasks on AI-assisted platforms. AI is super intelligent in AI- Led platform. Waymo One, a self driving technology based taxi developed by Google, is truly advancement of Artificial Intelligence. Activities of human on AI led platforms remain passive. ie humans are replaced by machines to complete the tasks for which human being do require intelligence and skills.

2.3. AI in Language Technology at Schools in Tashkent

AI is intrinsically connected to Language Teaching Technology. Scope of inclusion of AI- Led technology at various schools in Tashkent is remarkable. For instances AI powered smart board for Language Teaching has often lead to a creative, engaging, meaningful and productive learning. This has significant impact on all type of learners. Despite the fact, AI powered tools ease language learning, there is not much recognition for AI- assisted teaching learning from teachers, students, policy makers and stake holders. This is often due to potential issues they have happened to have during teaching of language, particularly in second language learning.

3. Some Potential Issues

AI's dependencies on intelligent algorithm have often unprecedented or expected issues arise. These are generally unaddressed. For a depth understanding, issues discussed on AI assisted language Technology are categorized B-W-A (Before, While and After).

3.1.B- Issues

Before using AI- powered tools for language learning, exists grim concern over the introduction AI- assisted technological aids to the class rooms. Some of them are:

3.1.1. Ethical and Social

This comprises of aversion of retiring policy makers, parents and even participants to technological advancements. For them, traditional ways of instruction are superior to AI based language technology and assume only private sectors excel through AI. Private tech organizations like IBM, Google, Wipro have been advancing and playing major role in current learning system. Little scope for ethical and social concerns is given. Changing technology results in meaningful learning outcomes. Continuous efforts for general acceptability and inclusion of technology are highly recommended.

3.1.2. Financing and Monitoring

Being an innovative technology, smart board is in great demand in digital market. AI-Powered teaching technology costs a large sum of money. Most of schools in Tashkent, therefore, have not been stepping up to introduce AI-assisted pedagogy in institutions like school, colleges and universities. However, a handful top rated public educational institutions run on AI-assisted technology, with proper monitoring with a vision of world class instruction makes differences.

3.1.3. Lack of Increased Research on AI -Assisted Learning Tools

Little and limited knowledge on AI-assisted tools has been available only for the few. Performance quality, scarce of

appropriate AI powered tools and lack of knowledge to incorporate in the field of language teaching are always threats to the educators. In the AI controlled world, an increased research on AI-powered tool is due.

3.2. W(hile)- Issues

Issues that keep on emerging even after inclusion of AI- powered language technology in curriculum. Listed below falls under While –Issue category

3.2.1. Heavy and Sophisticated data

When analyzed AI-assisted tools in Language teaching, a heavier and much sophisticated data than you imagine is seen applied to algorithm for better performance and quality output. Heaviness of data has often lead to complexity to technology.

3.2.2. Disruptive technology

AI powered Language Teaching is only possible on intelligent algorithm which is intrinsically sophisticated. Many instances of start over and over of the course due to malfunctioning of AI-built tools. This can somehow be resolved if quality backup and update of technology is done regularly.

3.2.3. Incorrect outcomes

Inaccurate data entries generate incorrect outcomes. Much repetitive attention and extreme care to be borne in mind while teaching AI for what to deliver promptly upon certain commands. For instances, incorrect pragmatic meaning outcomes we get on machine readable dictionary due to application of inaccurate data.

3.3. A(fter) - Issues

Potential problems arise not only before or while using AI-powered smart board. Some issues emerge post induction of it. They are considered as A- Challenges. A few of them are:-

3.3.1. Shortage of AI- Specialists

The supply of proficient and skilled of AI specialists has been a major issue for the public educational authorities. Since the evolution of AI- powered Language Technology, comparatively a very few language educators are available in developing countries. Very often, specialists tend to serve for AI-led countries like the U.S.A, China, Singapore e t. c for financial benefits.

3.3.2. Limited Professional Training

Majority of middle aged teachers believe technology has failed to transform classes. Becker (2000) view technology use by teachers was related to teachers' belief in more student –centered classrooms. AI- assisted tools can just be passive teaching material if teachers fail to understand roles of AI- powered materials. Professional workshops or development programs on using AI-powered language teaching is thus mandatory and imperative.

3.3.3. Inability of AI's Understanding Cognition level

Development of cognitive skills of participants is of high importance in Language Learning. AI assisted technology effectively reads the input it receives and responds accordingly. Little importance and scope for cognitive skills of learners but mechanical is seen on AI- assisted platforms.

4. Conclusion

The use of Artificial Intelligent Powered technology continues in

language class rooms of in the capital city of Uzbekistan, and rapid transformation in all phases of learning is apparently seen. Optimized AI integrated teaching- learning seldom does take place in a number of schools in Tashkent, even after installation of smart boards in class rooms, language labs and blue tooth TVs which are a million dollar funded projects by developed countries including the USA, Germany, Japan and China. Transition from typical teachers to tech-savvy teachers is rarely appreciated, attendance of teachers at Professional Development Programs is slim, attitude towards paper-less teaching- learning is hardly seen, and persistent collaboration towards set goals of smart and IT integrated teaching is minimum. The now and future of learning is undoubtedly a differentiated AI- powered teaching. Unless aforesaid issues are purposefully addressed and resolved, little impacts and results can be had. Additionally, AI- driven tools shall continue to be implemented for optimized language teaching- learning not only in private schools but public too.

References

1. Ahmadi, D. M. R. (2018). The use of technology in English language learning: A literature review. *International journal of research in English education*, 3(2), 115-125.
2. Becker, H. J. (2000). Findings from the teaching, learning, and computing survey. *Education policy analysis archives*, 8, 51-51.
3. Ferrucci, D. (2000). *Artificial Intelligence and Literary Creativity*. New Jersey;Lawrence Earlbaum Associates.
4. Bruner, J. S. (2009). *Actual minds, possible worlds*. Harvard university press.
5. Ilkka, T. (2018). *The impact of artificial intelligence on learning, teaching, and education*. European Union.